
Investigation into the Effectiveness of Bioagent-Enhanced Phytoremediation: A Case Study of Organic Soap and Charcoal

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Abstract

This Study was aimed at the possibility of using sustainable materials in carrying out environmental remediation. The methodologies involved were collection of uncontaminated soil samples, impacting it with crude oil at a ratio of 8:2 (by mass proportion), and remediating the polluted soil with local soap solution and wood charcoal. Outcomes of the laboratory tests indicated that, the crude oil caused insignificant increment in the Lead “Pb”, Nickel “Ni” and Copper “Cu”, and the concentrations were higher than the WHO standard. Notably, the Pb concentration increased from 6.53 to 21.93 mg/kg; the Ni content increased from 7.67 to 18.57 mg/kg, and the Cu level surged from 2.80 to 18.98 mg/kg. Likewise, it was noted that the remediating materials were able to downgrade the heavy metals levels, and assisted the phytoremediation of the contaminated soil samples. The soil samples remediated with combined treatment regime had the maximum remediation efficiency, recording 63.5% reduction in the Pb concentration, 56.3% Ni reduction, and 84% reduction in the Cu concentration. These results have highlighted that phytoremediation of petroleum contaminated can be successfully enhanced, through the utilization of locally available material like organic soap and wood charcoal.

Keywords: Environmental protection, petroleum, public health, remediation, sustainability

Introduction

Petroleum exploration, production and utilization are significant contributors to environmental pollution and degradation (Ukhurebor *et al.*, 2021). These anthropogenic activities discharges volumes of toxic materials into the environments, which tend to distort the natural habitats, human health, and climatic conditions. Crude oil contains numerous toxic chemicals, and other pollutants, which are harmful to the aquatic terrestrial ecosystems. Oil spills disturb the wildlife and vegetative cover, leading to erosion and pollution related challenges (Chinedu and Chukwuemeka, 2018; Asif *et al.*, 2022). Emissions from petroleum and its derivatives contribute immensely to acidic precipitations formation, respiratory illnesses, and other public health issues (Alharthy *et al.*, 2025).

It has been documented that the volatile fractions of petroleum hydrocarbons have an influential role in reducing germination and delaying seed emergence (Bahar *et al.*, 2024). Petroleum hydrocarbons pollutants in the soil can caused disruptions of natural equilibrium between the plants and animals and their ecosystems. Hydrocarbon contamination of the ecosystems has drawn public concerns because many hydrocarbons contaminants are highly toxic, neurotoxic, mutagenic, and carcinogenic (Koshlaf and Ball, 2017). Akpokodje *et al.*(2015), observed significant increment in the petroleum hydrocarbons concentration of soil samples polluted with petroleum oil, when compared with results obtained from unpolluted soil samples. These harmful impacts of petroleum pollution have necessitated the need to develop good remediation strategies.

Phytoremediation is a sustainable and eco-friendly remediation approach, which uses green plants to remediate the polluted environment. This method influences the natural capabilities of plants to reduce the pollutant concentration, thereby stabilizing the ecosystems - soil, water, and air. This provides sustainable information on mitigating the challenges caused by the pollution to human activities (Uguru and Udubra, 2021; Kafle *et al.*, 2022). Principally, phytoremediation contributes immensely in fightingthe hazards associated with environmental pollution and climate change. Apart from degradation of the contaminants, plants have the ability to requisition carbon dioxide (CO₂), which is a major greenhouse gas from the environment. Plants with rapid growth rates and high biomass are potent phytoremediation agents, primarily due to their higher ability to absorb large amounts of CO₂ and other pollutants from the environment (Aryal, 2024; Wijekoon *et al.*, 2025).

Microbialactivity enhances phytoremediation effectiveness, since this increases the soil fertility and plant performance. Lee *et al.* (2025) stated that microbial processes increase the soil health and oxygenation status; hence, increasing the phytoremediation efficacy; hence, preventing degradation and accumulation of hydrocarbons, toxic metals, and other poisonous substances in the ecosystems. Phytoremediation is among the most environmentally sustainable remediation techniques, as it relied mainly on organic materials and simple procedures, thereby lowering the reliance on synthetic materials, consequently reducing the volume of carbon footprint associated with environmental remediation (Akpokodje *et al.*, 2019; Kumaret *et al.*, 2024).Additionally, phytoremediation method can be incorporated into other environmental management tactics, which can help to reestablish degraded environs; thus, creating safer environments from contaminated sites.

Numerous remediation approaches have been developed by scholars recently (Akpokodje *et al.* 2019; Ilaboya and Onaiwu, 2020; Kafle *et al.* 2022; Aryal, 2024), and they tend to use different biomaterials to achieve their goals. A thorough related literature review revealed no significant information on the hybridization of bio-absorbent and bio-stimulant in the

phytoremediation of petroleum contaminated soil. Therefore, primary aim of this research is improving the phytoremediation efficiency of giant star grass, through the incorporation of wood charcoal and organic soap. The findings of this experimental investigation will be useful in the development of advance bioremediation techniques.

2.0 Materials and Methods

Samples collection and preparation

Uncontaminated soil was dug (0 – 0.6 m depth) with a spade, from a virgin land having no history of petroleum spills for the last 20 years. The soil was taken to the laboratory for drying in the Laboratory for analysis. The wood charcoal blocks were procured from the market located at Ozoro, Isoko North LGA of Delta State, Nigeria.

Local soap preparation

Oil palm bunch waste was collected from the oil mill of Delta State University of Science and Technology, Ozoro. The waste was dried in the sun before they were burnt into ashes; and the ashes were dissolved in distill water to obtain a heterogeneous solution. The filtrate obtained was evaporated and used to prepare the local soap as described by (Eboibi *et al.* 2018).

Soil contamination

The soil used for this research work was contaminated with crude oil (recovered from oil spill sites) at a ratio of 8:1. This means 8 parts (by mass) of the soil was impacted with 2 parts of crude oil.

Remediation procedure

The polluted soil was air dried in the laboratory at ambient temperature ($30\pm 4^{\circ}\text{C}$) for two weeks, and sifted using a 2 mm sieve. 15 kg of the contaminated soil was filled into plastic containers, and arranged according to the experimental setups, as shown in Table 1. The charcoal blocks were inserted into the contaminated soil sample inside the plastic buckets. In the organic soap treatment, the organic soap was divided into two equal parts. One part was thoroughly mixed with the soil sample to obtain a homogeneity mixture; while the other part was dissolved in one litre of distilled water to form a homogeneity mixture, before it was poured gently into plastic container containing the contaminated soil sample.

One stand of young giant star grass were transplanted into each plastic buckets containing the treated and untreated contaminated soils. All the plastic containers (control and treated) were placed in an open space, under atmospheric condition (rainfall, sunlight, relative humidity, temperature, dew, etc.) for an experimental period of 12 weeks. During the period, the containers were moderately watered when necessary to keep the soils moist. Weeding was done by handpicking throughout the experimental period.

Table 1: Experimental set up

Treatment	Materials used
T1	10 kg contaminated soil (Control)
T2	10 kg contaminated soil + 500 g charcoal block
T3	10 kg contaminated soil + 500 g organic soap
T4	10 kg contaminated soil + 500 g charcoal block + 500 g organic soap

Heavy metals (HMs) analysis

At the end of the experimental period, random soil samples were taken (0 – 0.2 m depth) from the buckets and coded. This depth is considered the rhizosphere region of the plants.

Rhizosphere region is the region of the soil closest to the plant's root which is under the direct influence of the root system. All the soil samples collected were air-dried and sieved with a 2 mm sieve before the soil analysis. The collected soil samples were stored individually in amber glass bottles, and transported immediately to the laboratory for chemical analysis. In the laboratory, the soil samples were coded and air dried at ambient laboratory temperature ($32\pm 4^{\circ}\text{C}$) for two weeks. Then the dried soil samples were then crushed and sieved before digestion. The dried soil samples were grounded and sieved with a 2 mm filter.

The STM D1971/4691 standard procedure was used to determine heavy metals (Pb, Cu, and Ni) concentrations of the soil samples. 10 g of the sieved sample was transferred into a round bottom conical flask, and digested with a mixture of concentrated HNO_3 , HCl , and H_2SO_4 - mixed at a ratio of 5:1:1. The digested sample was then filtered with a Whatman No. 42 filter paper, and the filtrate poured into a volumetric flask, before it was diluted with distilled water up to 100 ml calibration. Then an Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS) was used to measure the concentration of the heavy metals digested soils samples.

Statistical analysis

The relationship between the remediating agents and petroleum contamination was determined with Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) by using the SPSS statistical software (version 20.0, SPSS Inc, Chicago, IL). The mean was separated using Duncan's Multiple Range Tests at 95% confidence level. All the experiments were replicated three times, and the average values recorded.

3.0 Results and Discussion

Effect of the petroleum on the heavy metals content

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) result of the effect of the petroleum products on the soil heavy metals concentrations is presented in Table 2. The ANOVA results revealed that the petroleum products had significant effect ($p \leq 0.05$) on the heavy metals concentrations of the soil samples. The descriptive results given in Table 3 showed that the lead concentration increased from 6.53 to 21.93 mg/kg; the nickel concentration increased from 7.67 to 18.57 mg/kg; while the copper concentration increased from 2.80 to 18.98 mg/kg. This result depicted that petroleum products can negatively affect the heavy metals concentrations of soils samples. Uguru *et al.* (2023) stated that petroleum hydrocarbons content in the soils can affect the physicochemical properties of the soil which may in turn affect the agricultural potentials and productivities of such soils. Similar result trend was reported by Akpokodje and Uguru (2019), where lead concentration increased from 0.001 to 1.128 mg/kg, the copper concentration increased from 4.892 to 7.729 mg/kg, and the iron concentration increased from 1251.2 to 1587.9 mg/kg. Petroleum hydrocarbons pollution can render soils unproductive for years after spillage, reducing the growth, performance and productivity of most plants (Ilaboya and Onaiwu, 2020).

Table 2: ANOVA results of the effect of petroleum of soil HMs content

Source		Sum of Squares	Df	M S	F	p-value
Pb	Between Groups	355.89	1	355.894	534.48	2.07E-05*
	Within Groups	2.66	4	0.66		
	Total	358.57	5			
Ni	Between Groups	178.22	1	178.21	243.02	9.88E-05*
	Within Groups	2.93	4	0.73		
	Total	181.148	5			
Cu	Between Groups	393.01	1	393.01	2075.95	1.38E-06*
	Within Groups	0.75	4	0.19		
	Total	393.77	5			

* = not significant at $p \leq 0.05$

Table 3: Effect of crude oil on the HMs concentration(mg/kg)

Parameter		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error	Min	Max
Lead	Virgin soil	6.53	1.14	0.66	5.83	7.85
	Contaminated soil	21.93	0.15	0.09	21.80	22.10
Nickel	Virgin soil	7.67	0.56	0.33	7.20	8.30
	Contaminated soil	18.57	1.06	0.62	17.40	19.50
Copper	Virgin soil	2.80	0.30	0.17	2.50	3.10
	Contaminated soil	18.98	0.54	0.31	18.48	19.55

Effect of Treatment on the Heavy Metals Content

The effect of remediation on the heavy metals contents of the soil is shown in Figure.1. As revealed in Figure 1, the lead, nickel and copper concentration of the contaminated and uncontaminated soil samples declined at the end of the experimental period. The declined the heavy metals concentrations observed in the untreated contaminated soil at the end of the experimental period could be attributed to the weathering of the petroleum products. According to International Tanker Owners Pollution Federation Limited (ITOPFL), when oil remains in the environment for an extended period of time, it undergoes a continuous series of compositional changes that are results of a process known as weathering (Ülker *et al.*, 2022). The contaminated soil samples treated with combined treatment regime (T4) had the lowest lead, nickel and copper concentration of 8.02 mg/kg, 8.12 mg/kg and 3.05 mg/kg, respectively at the end of the experimental period. This was closely followed by the contaminated soil samples treated with charcoal block, which had lead, nickel and copper concentration of 9.81 mg/kg, 8.31 mg/kg and 5.48 mg/kg, respectively at the end of the experimental period. Similarly, the contaminated soil samples that were treated with local soap had 13.22 mg/kg of lead, 8.95 mg/kg of nickel and 5.93 mg/kg of copper, in the soil at the end of the experimental period. The revealed that combined treatment is a better remediation option, compared to the single treatment option. Similar results were reported by Akpokodje and Uguru (2019), during the remediation of petroleum hydrocarbons contaminated soils with compost manure and local soap sousing okra and fluted pumpkin plants. According to Akpokodje and Uguru (2019), copper content in petroleum products contaminated soil remediated with okra and organic manure declined from 7.73 to 5.97 mg/kg within a 14 week experimental period.

Figure 4.1: Remediation potency of various treatment regimes

During the phytoremediation, the charcoal blocks tend to absorb most of the petroleum hydrocarbons, thereby energizing the hydrocarbons degrading microorganisms, and proper growth and development of the grain star grass. Apart from the de-emulsification of petroleum products by the local soap during the bioremediation process, the soap is rich in essential nutrients - Nitrogen, potassium and phosphorus, which provide suitable environment for the soil microorganisms' performance. Nitrogen and phosphorus compounds accelerate the biodegradation of the petroleum hydrocarbon in the soil (Akpokodje and Uguru, 2019; Mirsaeidi, 2023; Alharthy *et al.*, 2025). Soil microorganisms require macronutrients (mostly nitrogen) in higher concentration and also micronutrients to degrade crude oil contaminated soil; and for successful phytoremediation both plants and microbes must survive and grow in the contaminated soil. Plants roots help to provide an ideal environment for degradation of toxic compounds, as they allow rapid movement of water and gases through the soil, and provide a biologically active soil region, which encourages microbial activity and enhances bioavailability (Zhakypbek *et al.*, 2024). The contribution to knowledge is that contaminated soil from oil spillage by hydrocarbon can undergo bioremediation using locally available material like organic soap as used in this work. Phytoremediation is a means of reducing the effects of greenhouse gases and climate change crises.

4.0 Conclusion

This study focused on the possibility of using natural absorbents and simulants, to enhance the phytoremediation potential of giant star grass. During the experimental investigation, petroleum contaminated soil was remediated with the combination of wood charcoal, organic soil and giant star grass. The study's findings indicated that the petroleum negatively affect the heavy metals levels in the soil, by increasing their concentrations. Furthermore, the experimental outcomes highlighted that the giant star grass was a potent phytoremediation agent, and the phytoremediation effectiveness of the plant, was enhanced by the organic materials. Specifically, this research outcome highlights the sustainability and efficacy of using eco-friendly biomaterials for the remediation of crude oil contaminated environments

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